

Bootstrapping Gapped theory with Gravitational Dressing and Wavepacket Positivity

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Bootstrap and positivity techniques are most effective for gapped amplitudes whose high-energy growth obeys the Froissart bound. In realistic theories, however, graviton exchange is unavoidable and induces a universal long-range infrared dressing. We develop a framework that factorizes the conservative (1–2)PM eikonal dressing directly in impact-parameter space and defines an “undressed” amplitude that inherits the unitarity and analyticity of the dressed amplitude. This separation maps generic EFT contact interactions into compact-support contributions in b -space. We further introduce a wavepacket-smearing representation in which a Gaussian wavepacket appears as a special case and yields a bootstrap implementation of UV positivity without parameter tuning. This provides a natural bridge toward bootstrapping AdS/QCD and UV completion of gravity, where Gaussian profiles arise from transverse diffusion. Overall, the wavepacket shape and size offer a direct handle for constraining low-energy EFTs, and our results give a practical route to short-distance physics in the presence of universal gravitational dressing.

INTRODUCTION

Positivity bounds and bootstrap methods provide sharp, UV-sensitive constraints on low-energy Wilson coefficients for SM (or BSM) scattering, relying on analyticity, crossing, and unitarity.[1] In four dimensions, however, gravity is never truly switchable: even if the short-distance sector is gapped and weakly coupled, massless graviton exchange generates a universal long-range tail. In the (near)-forward limit this manifests already at tree level through the t -channel $1/t$ singularity, while loop corrections from the virtual soft-graviton region generate infrared logarithms. Starting at 3PM, genuine gravitational radiation introduces additional (soft) IR-sensitive contributions, so the dispersive sum rules used to constrain Wilson coefficients can be contaminated by long-distance physics, obscuring which part of a bound is genuinely UV and which part is a byproduct of universal gravitational dressing.[2? ? ?]

In this Letter we focus on the conservative (radiation-free) sector through 1PM and 2PM, where the eikonal exponentiation provides a controlled description of elastic scattering.[3? , 4] Incorporating radiative effects at 3PM requires an IR-safe treatment of soft emission, e.g. by summing over degenerate soft radiation in inclusive observables or by dressing asymptotic states so that the S -matrix captures IR-finite hard content.[5, 6] For bootstrap purposes, this motivates an IR-safe formulation of the amplitude itself, rather than imposing an *ad hoc* IR cutoff Λ_{IR} inside dispersive sum rules.

We propose a practical route to such an IR-safe bootstrap by factorizing the *universal gravitational dressing* directly in impact-parameter space. Working in the eikonal regime, we separate the amplitude into a conservative eikonal phase factor and an “undressed” remainder that captures short-distance (local) dynamics while inheriting unitarity and analyticity properties from the full dressed amplitude. A key advantage is that local EFT interactions become contact (compact-support) contribu-

tions in b -space, so UV positivity constraints can be imposed on the undressed data without being dominated by IR graviton physics.

We also introduce a more physical, geometrical way to control the IR. The logarithmic divergence originates from integrating the long-range r^{-1} potential, so placing the same UV-complete theory on a spacetime with finite transverse volume provides an intrinsic IR regulator. Concretely, we consider $\mathbb{M}^{1,1} \times S^2$ with sphere radius B : the global geometry modifies the IR scattering data associated with massless graviton exchange, while leaving local contact terms insensitive. We then find that although the low-energy side of the dispersion relation receives both graviton and local EFT contributions, their UV support on the real s -axis is well separated: the EFT sector is concentrated near $s \sim \Lambda^2$, whereas the gravitational dressing is controlled by $s \sim (G_N \log(B/b))^{-1}$. This separation allows a piecewise dispersive analysis that cleanly disentangles long-range and short-range physics.

Beyond light external states such as axions, photons, and neutrinos, bounds on *local* graviton EFTs have become increasingly relevant in the era of gravitational-wave phenomenology. The positive time-delay constraint severely restricts higher-derivatives of the graviton 3-point coupling and, implies that they must be an infinite tower of massive higher-spin states at a scale comparable to where the higher-derivative corrections become important.[7?] In contrast, this work targets the *local* 4-point EFT with cutoff Λ , in the regime $\sqrt{-t} \lesssim \Lambda$, which does not probe the high-energy completion responsible for restoring time-delay. We therefore package all conservative long-range gravitational effects—including those encoded in any time-delay-consistent 3-point structures (R^3 , RF^2 , and $\eta R\bar{R}$)—into the universal eikonal dressing factor. The remaining “undressed” amplitude is then the appropriate object to bootstrap, leading to IR-safe constraints on local 4-point operators for processes such as $hhhh$, $hh\gamma\gamma$, etc.

Finally, our framework applies to *arbitrary external*

states. For a generic four-point local interaction, the undressed data are precisely the short-distance contact terms. Locality implies a characteristic support property in impact-parameter space: the contact contribution is a distribution supported at $b = 0$, i.e. a linear combination of derivatives of the transverse delta function, schematically $s^m t^n \sim s^m (\nabla_b^2)^n \delta^{(2)}(\mathbf{b})$. [8]

Building on this separation, we propose a “wavepacket bootstrap” viewpoint: instead of scattering two idealized pointlike states, we consider a reference pointlike probe against a wavepacket state. The smearing effectively gives the local EFT data, and a distinguished Gaussian wavepacket yields a particularly simple positivity structure. No matter whether in eikonal regime ($|s| \gg |t|$ or $|s| \sim |t|$), it makes the relevant s - and u -channel spectral contributions positive, i.e. coefficients of partial-wave expansions are always positive, allowing us to bypass the usual tuning of subtraction schemes or test functions that is often needed to enforce UV positivity. Varying the wavepacket shape and size then generates a family of sum rules, providing a direct and flexible handle for constraining low-energy EFT.

GRAVITATIONAL EIKONAL DRESSING

We start from the eikonal regime $s \gg -q^2$ of 4-massless scattering in all-outgoing convention, where particle-2, 4 are same particle with no helicity flip, while 1, 3 are two general particles. The momentum transfer \mathbf{q} is Fourier conjugate to the impact parameter \mathbf{b} . In this regime, long-range interactions mediated by massless exchange admit an exponentiated representation in impact-parameter space: the infinite set of ladder and crossed-ladder diagrams built from a given exchange kernel reorganizes into an eikonal phase. [3, 4, 9?] We will also include weakly coupled short-distance contact interactions in the same b -space description. Their contribution defines a “local phase” $\delta_{\text{loc}}(s, b)$, but in the weak-coupling limit we retain only the leading term, while resumming the long-range exchange to all orders.

Concretely, we write the dressed amplitude as

$$\text{FT} \left[\frac{\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}(s + i\varepsilon, \mathbf{q})}{2s} \right] = \mathcal{M}(s + i\varepsilon, \mathbf{b}) = e^{i\delta_{\text{eik}}(s+i\varepsilon, \mathbf{b})} - 1, \quad (1)$$

where $\delta_{\text{eik}}(s, b)$ collects the dynamics. In the PM expansion,

tion,

$$\delta_{\text{eik}}(s, b) = \delta_{\text{loc}}(s, b) + \delta_0(s, b) + \delta_1(s, b) + \dots, \quad (2)$$

$$\delta_{\text{loc}}(s, b) = \text{FT} \left[e^{i(h_1+h_3)\phi_q} \sum c_{\text{mn}} s^m t^n \right] = e^{i(h_1+h_3)\phi_b} \sum c_{\text{mn}} s^m \nabla_b^{2n} \quad (3)$$

$$\delta_0(s, b) = -Gs \left(\mathbf{1} + \kappa_g \partial_{b_-}^2 |\eta\rangle \langle h^+| + \kappa_g^* \partial_{b_+}^4 |h^+\rangle \langle \eta| + \dots \right) \log(|b|/\Lambda) \quad (4)$$

$$\delta_1(s, b) = G^2 \frac{s}{b^2} \log(s) + \text{helicity-flip terms}. \quad (5)$$

with δ_0 determined by tree-level exchange and $\delta_{2\text{PM}}$ by the one-loop contribution. [4, 9? ?] Both terms contribute only a *phase* to the S -matrix. In the regime where quantum corrections are small, $G/b^2 \ll 1$, and where black-hole production is parametrically suppressed, $G^2 s/b^2 \ll 1$, the 2PM contribution is parametrically subleading, $\delta_{2\text{PM}} \ll \delta_{1\text{PM}}$, [4, 9?] and is free of infrared divergences. For this reason, we retain only the 1PM contribution in the analysis below.

We emphasize that $\delta_{1\text{PM}}$ is not restricted to the minimal Einstein coupling. It also includes graviton exchange induced by helicity-flipping three-point interactions such as R^3 , RF^2 , and ηRR . Introducing complex transverse coordinates $b_{\pm} = b_x \pm ib_y$ makes the helicity structure manifest: these couplings modify the tensorial numerator of the graviton t -channel pole rather than canceling it. For example, in the presence of a gravitational anomaly coefficient κ_g , the analytic structure near the t -pole takes the schematic form $q_+^2/(q_+q_-)$.

We now package the full eikonal phase δ_{eik} into a single *grey blob*, whose multi-insertion and all possible crossed-ladder combinations are resummed into the exponential appearing in the impact-parameter space.

$$\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}(s, b) = \text{grey blob} + \text{grey blob} \text{ grey blob} + \text{grey blob} \text{ grey blob} \text{ grey blob} + \dots \quad (6)$$

The specific Feynman diagram of the interactions between the grey blob at 1PM, 2PM, and local is as follows:

$$\text{grey blob} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{1} \text{---} \text{blue blob} \text{---} \text{3} \\ \text{2} \text{---} \text{wavy line} \text{---} \text{4} \end{array} , \begin{array}{l} \text{1} \text{---} \text{blue blob} \text{---} \text{3} \\ \text{2} \text{---} \text{wavy line} \text{---} \text{4} \end{array} , \text{white blob} \right\} \quad (7)$$

We use blue blobs to mark valid vertices resulting from gravitational minimum coupling and the three-point EFT, and white blob only resulting from minimal coupling; while black indicates an 4-pt EFT truncated with Λ as the energy scale. In fact, when $b \lesssim \Lambda^{-1}$, local interactions also have fine structure, at which point the EFT approximation does not hold, and high-spin states that generate these local interactions will be encountered in the t -channel.

For the local phase, in momentum space it is analytic around $t = 0$; in impact-parameter space it becomes delta functions and derivatives supported at $b \simeq 0$. In the

weak-coupling limit we keep only a *single* insertion of δ_{loc} , while resumming arbitrarily many long-range graviton exchanges.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}(s + i\varepsilon, b) &= \left(e^{i\delta_0(s,b)} - 1 \right) + i e^{i\delta_0(s,b)} \delta_{\text{loc}}(s, b) + \dots, \\ &= \text{[diagram 1]} + \text{[diagram 2]} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where the ellipsis denotes either higher powers of the local interaction. Throughout this paper we focus on the conservative eikonal dressing through 1 and 2PM. Starting at 3PM, genuine gravitational radiation introduces dissipative effects, and a fully IR-safe treatment requires an inclusive summation [9?] or Faddeev-Kulish dressed states, We leave the systematic incorporation of radiative corrections to future work.

If we set the soft scale as \sqrt{t} , analogous to the Soft Factor, then the gravitational contribution to the entire eikonal amplitude can be viewed as infinitely many soft gravitons attached to the rails of an original amplitude. We refer to this procedure as *eikonal dressing*, which is exactly the eikonal limit of the dressing factor in [10, 11].

Note that the soft graviton dressing of the local amplitude [10] involves both an radiation factor and a phase factor whose leading contributions scale as $G^{0.5}$ and G^1 , respectively, so they enter observables like cross sections and discontinuities at the same order. By contrast, for the eikonal amplitude the graviton dressing [12] has a radiation factor of order $G^{1.5}$ and a phase factor of order G^1 , which delays any radiation effects until the 3PM calculation. So here 1-2PM analysis of this chapter there are no radiation factors.

We will now show that, for any gapped theory satisfying the Froissart bound, bootstrapping $\delta_{\text{loc}}(s, b)$ is equivalent to bootstrapping the full amplitude in Eq. (8), leading to identical bounds.

Graviton Dressing Won't Lead to Negativity

Although both in QFT and string theory we can place the same theory in finite space to better probe it, for comparison with other works we will also bootstrap the amplitudes including gravity in flat space. Our conclusion differs from [13, 14]: we argue that adding gravity to scattering does not lead to a small negativity. Negativity is because these works are effectively bootstrapping the combination of gravity and QFT, rather than isolating them.

The undressed amplitude only exists in finite space; in infinite flat space, the amplitude always comes with a graviton dressing factor, eq.(?). This dressing introduces new discontinuities by modifying eq.(?) into (8).

Their relation is

$$\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{dressed}}(s + i\varepsilon, b) = i(1 - e^{i\delta_0}) + e^{i\delta_0} \cdot \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{undressed}}(s + i\varepsilon, b). \quad (9)$$

The first term is the pure gravity contribution. The second term contains the **imaginary part of the amplitude modified by dressing**, and its **real part also develops ripples due to loop effects**. In the toy model with a massive scalar, eq. (22) shows that positivity is restored in 4-photon scattering, but not in the ill-behaved 4-graviton case with a boundary, eq. (27).

The advantage of the toy model is that we know not only the residue of the amplitude at $s = m^2$ but also its principal value (PV) for arbitrary complex s . In general, however, the PV is unknown. The undressed amplitude in eq. (9), divided by s^2 , defines a function on the complex s -plane which can be decomposed as a sum over poles (branch cuts) plus a holomorphic function $H(s, b)$ without singularities.[15] Most generally, whether for graviton, photon or scalar scattering, we always have

$$\oint_{C_\infty} \frac{ds}{2\pi i} \frac{\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{undressed}}(s, b)}{s^2} = \text{Res}_{\text{tot}}(b). \quad (10)$$

Then \mathcal{M}/s^2 can be written as

$$\frac{\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{undressed}}(s, b)}{s^2} = \frac{\text{Res}_{\text{tot}}(b)}{s} + \sum_i \left(-\frac{\text{Res}(m_i^2, b)}{s} + \frac{\text{Res}(m_i^2, b)}{s - m_i^2} \right) + \quad (11)$$

Since the high-energy growth of amplitude is polynomial bounded and does not exhibit exponential divergence, i.e. $H(s, b) < |s|^N$, then we have

$$\oint_{C_\infty} \frac{ds}{2\pi i} \frac{e^{i\delta_0(s,b)} \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{undressed}}(s, b)}{s^2} = 0. \quad (12)$$

We expand around $s = 0$ to pick up the residue

$$\oint_{C_0} \frac{ds}{2\pi i} \frac{e^{i\delta_0(s,b)} \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{undressed}}(s, b)}{s^2} = \sum_i \text{Res}(m_i^2, b) - \text{Res}_{\text{tot}}(b). \quad (13)$$

which is unchanged compared with undressed one. In other words, if we arrange for a negative residue at $s = 0$ and a positive one at $s = m^2$, then under dressing the residue at $s = 0$ remains unchanged, while the other one splits into the **dressed residue** and **ripples**, whose sum exactly equals the original positive residue. Hence the positivity from undressed amplitude is preserved. The only issue arises if $\text{Res}_{\text{tot}}(b) > 0$, for then its negative **ripple** produced by dressing would spoil positivity.

Therefore, for the undressed amplitude with vanishing 2SDR boundary (i.e. $\text{Res}_{\text{tot}} = 0$, guaranteed by Froissart bound), the bound is not weakened when including graviton exchanges, but remains the same. The difference from [13] is that they used

$$\text{Im} \left[i(1 - e^{i\delta_0}) + e^{i\delta_0} \cdot \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{undressed}} \right] \geq 0. \quad (14)$$

and furthermore approximate that the Disc in region $|s| \leq \Lambda^2$ only come from gravity, then they derive the relaxed bound $g_2 + 1/\Lambda^2 > 0$.

By actually, since dressing preserves the C_0 integral and enforces the C_∞ integral to vanish, the dressed amplitude inherits the positivity of the undressed amplitude,

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Im}[e^{i\delta_0} \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{undressed}}] \not\geq 0, \\ & \int \frac{ds}{s^2} \text{Im}[e^{i\delta_0} \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{undressed}}] = \int \frac{ds}{s^2} \text{Im}[\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{undressed}}] \geq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Hence, involving graviton loops in scattering does not change the original bound $g_2 > 0$.

Probing a UV Toy Model

In this section we add a massive scalar into the pure-gravity scattering processes $\gamma^+\gamma^+\gamma^-\gamma^-$ and $h^+h^+h^-h^-$, to test the feasibility of the two bootstrap ways.

4-photon Scattering

We begin by computing the UV contribution to the eikonal phase using eq. (??),

$$M_{\text{UV}}(s, b) = \int \frac{d^2\mathbf{q}}{8\pi^2 s} e^{-i\mathbf{b}\cdot\mathbf{q}} |g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2 \frac{[12]^2 \langle 34 \rangle^2}{s - m^2} = |g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2 \frac{s}{(m^2 - s)b^2}, \quad (16)$$

where we used the on-shell identity [16] $[12]^2 \langle 34 \rangle^2 = s^2$ and Fourier transform integral trick [17]. Now the Gravity-UV mixed eikonal amplitude in impact-parameter space becomes

$$\begin{aligned} 1 + i\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}(s + i\epsilon, b) &= \exp \left\{ i2Gs \log(1/b\Lambda_{\text{IR}}) + i \frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2 s}{(m^2 - s)b^2} \right\} \\ &\approx e^{i2Gs \log(1/b\Lambda_{\text{IR}})} \left(1 + i \frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2 s}{(m^2 - s)b^2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where in the second equality we have assumed $|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}| \ll b$ and perturbatively expanded to first order in $|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2$. The resulting change of the eikonal amplitude is

$$\Delta \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}(s, b) = e^{i2Gs \log(1/b\Lambda_{\text{IR}})} \frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2 s}{(m^2 - s)b^2}. \quad (18)$$

We then substitute the change in the amplitude into the 2DR

$$\int_{C_0} \frac{ds}{s^2} \Delta \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}(s, b) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{ds}{s^2} \text{Disc} [\Delta \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}(s, b)], \quad (19)$$

and compute the low-energy and high-energy contour separately. For $\gamma^+\gamma^+\gamma^-\gamma^-$ scattering, one EFT oper-

ator contributes to the C_0 integral,

$$\int_{C_0} \frac{ds}{s^2} \Delta \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}(s, b) = (2\pi i) \frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2}{m^2 b^2} \quad (20)$$

And for the high-energy contour integral, we first compute its discontinuity

$$\text{Disc} \Delta \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}} = (2i) \sin(\delta_0) \frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2 s}{(m^2 - s)b^2} + (2\pi i) \cos(\delta_0) \frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2 m^2}{b^2} \delta(s - m^2) \quad (21)$$

and then integrate to obtain

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{ds}{s^2} \text{Disc} \Delta \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}} = (2\pi i) \frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2}{m^2 b^2} \left(1 - \cos(\delta_0^{s=m^2}) \right) + (2\pi i) \frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2}{m^2 b^2} \quad (22)$$

One easily checks that the contour integral around C_0 of the EFT operator contribution coincides exactly with the sum of the s - and u -channel discontinuity integrals, so by Cauchy's theorem the boundary term must vanish. However, we also encounter two drawbacks:

- Discontinuity in Eq. (21) is not positive, both Sin and Cos oscillate rapidly with $\delta_0 = 2Gs \ln(1/b\Lambda_{\text{IR}})$, making it impossible to build useful bounds.
- The discontinuity now receives contributions from two kind of unitarity cuts:

$$\quad (23)$$

New discontinuities arise not only at the “UV stone's landing point”, $s = m^2$, but also elsewhere due to the “ripples” it creates. Sum of them exactly equals to the EFT contribution. This confirms that the mixed UV-gravity amplitude satisfy the 2DR boundary condition, i.e. $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{ds}{s^2} \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}} = 0$.

Whether due to the lack of positivity, or because the discontinuity no longer arises purely from the UV resonance cut but also includes elastic-channel cuts from its gravitational “ripples”, both issues indicate that bootstrapping the amplitude difference $\Delta \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}$ is not a good choice.

Next, we turn to bootstrap the undressed amplitude $\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{undressed}}$

$$1 + i\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{undressed}}(s + i\epsilon, b) = \exp \left\{ i \frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2 s}{(m^2 - s)b^2} \right\} = 1 + i \frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2 s}{(m^2 - s)b^2} + \dots \quad (24)$$

We immediately find

$$\int_{C_0} \frac{ds}{s^2} \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{undressed}} = (2\pi i) \frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2}{m^2 b^2} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{ds}{s^2} \text{Disc} \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{undressed}} \quad (25)$$

That is, for $\gamma^+\gamma^+\gamma^-\gamma^-$ scattering, even without graviton dressing, the boundary term vanishes. Although we

only displayed the leading effect of $g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}$, this cancellation between the C_0 and discontinuity integrals holds to all orders in the coupling. Moreover, the expression above is precisely the dispersion relation typically used in EFT bootstrap. For more complicated mass spectra, it can be used to bound Wilson coefficients.

This appears to be the right amplitude to bootstrap. A natural question then arises: for $h^+h^+h^-h^-$, where the 2SDR seems receive no EFT contribution to balance the positivity, so the boundary is nonzero?

4-graviton Scattering

Following a similar calculation as in the photon scattering case, we have

$$M'_{\text{UV}}(s, b) = \int \frac{d^2\mathbf{q}}{8\pi^2 s} e^{-i\mathbf{b}\cdot\mathbf{q}} |g_{hh\phi}|^2 \frac{[12]^4 \langle 34 \rangle^4}{s - m^2} = |g_{hh\phi}|^2 \frac{s^3}{(m^2 - s)b^2}, \quad (26)$$

and then bootstrap the variation $\Delta\mathcal{M}'_{\text{eik}}$ before and after adding the resonance. The result is

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{C_0} \frac{ds}{s^2} \Delta\mathcal{M}'_{\text{eik}} &= 0 \\ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{ds}{s^2} \text{Disc } \Delta\mathcal{M}'_{\text{eik}} &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{ds}{s^2} \left[(2i) \sin(\delta_0) \frac{|g_{hh\phi}|^2 s^3}{(m^2 - s)b^2} + (2\pi i) \frac{|g_{hh\phi}|^2 m^3}{\cos(\delta_0) \delta_0 (s - m^2)} \right] \\ &= -(2\pi i) \frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2 m^2}{b^2} \cos(\delta_0^{s=m^2}) + (2\pi i) \frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2 m^2}{b^2} \cos(\delta_0^{s=m^2}) \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

This shows that the variation $\Delta\mathcal{M}'_{\text{eik}}$ in graviton scattering also satisfies the 2DR with a vanishing boundary term. As in the photon case, the rapid oscillations from δ_0 destroy positivity, and there are also gravitational dressing effects—ripples. If we once again switch to the undressed amplitude,

$$1 + i\mathcal{M}'_{\text{eik}}{}^{\text{undressed}}(s + i\epsilon, b) = \exp \left\{ i \frac{|g_{hh\phi}|^2 s^3}{(m^2 - s)b^2} \right\} \quad (28)$$

we now find that the EFT contribution from the low-energy contour C_0 no longer matches the integral over the positive discontinuity. Instead, it is canceled by a nonzero boundary term,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{C_0} \frac{ds}{s^2} \mathcal{M}'_{\text{eik}}{}^{\text{undressed}} &= 0 \\ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{ds}{s^2} \text{Disc } \mathcal{M}'_{\text{eik}}{}^{\text{undressed}} &= (2\pi i) \frac{|g_{hh\phi}|^2 m^2}{b^2} \\ \int_{C_\infty} \frac{ds}{s^2} \mathcal{M}'_{\text{eik}}{}^{\text{undressed}} &= -(2\pi i) \frac{|g_{hh\phi}|^2 m^2}{b^2} \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

That is, for $h^+h^+h^-h^-$ scattering via a massive scalar, the undressed amplitude has a nonzero 2SDR boundary. Although the amplitude in eq. (28) remains $\mathcal{O}(1)$ along the real- s axis, its partial wave $a_l(s)$ has huge oscillations $\gg 1$. This exponential divergence in the complex

plane violates polynomial boundedness and thus unitarity. Therefore, one cannot naively analytically continue the tree-level form of eq. (26).

We summarize the dispersion relations discussed in this section with the following table:

2SDR	$\Delta\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}$	$\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{undressed}}$
$\gamma^+\gamma^+\gamma^-\gamma^-$	EFT = ripples + dressed resonance	EFT = resonance
$h^+h^+h^-h^-$	0 = ripples + dressed resonance	0 = resonance - b

For the dressed amplitude, regardless of whether the EFT is zero or not, the ripples always precisely cancel to ensure the boundary vanishes. This appears to support the conclusion from App. : No matter what UV is added, graviton dressing always suppresses the boundary contribution to zero.

We will show below that as long as the undressed amplitude has no boundary in its 2SDR, graviton dressing does not affect the EFT bootstrap bounds. Moreover, in Sec ?? we'll point out that $h^+h^+h^-h^-$ scattering in QCD is not as ill-behaved as in the toy model: the presence of gluon loops ensures a nonzero EFT contribution in the 2SDR.

Looking back at the Feynman diagrams of $\Delta\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}$ and $\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{undressed}}$ in eq. (8) and (??), we see that if we want to preserve positivity while exposing UV, the eikonal undressed amplitude might be a good option.

Physical Realization: Scattering in Finite Space

Above we defined the undressed amplitude by removing all gravitons with $|k| \lesssim \sqrt{t}$. A perfectly physical realization is scattering in a finite space—either a closed 4D curved spacetime or a lab sealed against gravitational waves—introducing a true IR cutoff.

Crucially, in finite-space scattering one cannot partial-wave expand using the usual Wigner d -functions, which are overlaps of spherical harmonics in infinite flat space. In a region of size B , $d_{h,h'}^J$ fails for partial waves with $J/\sqrt{s} \gtrsim B$. This breakdown underlies the small “negative” contributions observed in [18] at large impact parameter—but it does *not* signal a true violation of positivity. Writing the positivity conditions in partial-wave J bases and impact-parameter b ,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}_{\text{el.}}(s, t) &= \sum_J (2J + 1) \rho_J(s) \mathcal{P}_{h,h'}^J(1 + 2t/s), \quad 0 \leq \text{Im } \rho_J(s) \leq 2 \\ \mathcal{M}_{\text{el.}}(s, b) &= i \left(1 - \mathcal{S}_{\text{el.}}(s, b) \right), \quad 0 \leq \text{Im } \mathcal{M}_{\text{el.}}(s, b) \leq 2 \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

where $\mathcal{P}_{h,h'}^J$ are the true finite-volume partial waves (reducing to Wigner d -matrices only when $J/\sqrt{s} \ll B$). With identical in- and out-states, the optical theorem still guarantees positivity in finite volume.

But we actually don't have to partial-wave expand and smear—that was just a convenience for the large- N QCD

FIG. 1. Schematic diagram of C_0 , Disc integrals and C_∞ .

tree-level work. For elastic scattering, the amplitude is positive whether written in J or b . The only difference is describing the in/out states as waves of angular momentum J versus particle pairs at impact parameter b .

Back to the toy model, now we have $\log(B/b) \sim \mathcal{O}(1)$. First write down the amplitudes:

$$1 + i\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{4\gamma}(s + i\epsilon, b) = e^{i2Gs \log(B/b)} \left(1 + i \frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2 s}{(m^2 - s)b^2} \right) \quad (31)$$

Note that there is more than one contour choice for the 2DR since we have two scales, m^2 and $(G \log)^{-1}$. We can introduce a UV contour C_∞^{UV} where $m^2 \ll |s| \ll (G \log)^{-1}$, and a trans-Planckian contour C_∞^{TP} where $(G \log)^{-1} \ll |s|$ in Fig. 1. We will see that only C_∞^{UV} extracts the UV information we seek. Since the UV spectrum of QFT is independent of the space radius B , so the 2SDR still hold after taking n -th derivative with respect to $\log(B/b)$, which is equivalent to performing a series expansion in $G|s| \log(B/b)$. The leading term in this series is precisely the undressed amplitude.

$$\left[\frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2}{m^2 b^2} + 2G \log(B/b) \right]_{C_0} = \left[\frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2}{m^2 b^2} \right]_{\text{Disc}} + \left[2G \log(B/b) \right]_{C_\infty^{\text{UV}}} \quad (32)$$

In other words, the 2DR of undressed amplitude in eq. (29) is just the leading term of integral C_∞^{UV} and its inside discontinuity, which scales as $[\log(B/b)]^0$. The fact that $|s|$ is not taken to infinity is crucial for treating gravity perturbatively.

So what about C_∞^{TP} when $(G \log)^{-1} \ll |s|$? In that case the 2DR is precisely the bootstrap result for $\Delta\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}$ in eq. (22),

$$\left[\frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2}{m^2 b^2} + 2G \log(B/b) \right]_{C_0} = \left[\frac{|g_{\gamma\gamma\phi}|^2}{m^2 b^2} + 2G \log(B/b) \right]_{\text{Disc}} + \left[0 \right]_{C_\infty^{\text{TP}}} \quad (33)$$

When $G|s| \log \gg 1$, ladder graviton loops always make the boundary term in the 2DR drop to zero, whether the

spacetime is flat or curved. For the tree-level amplitude $\gamma^+ \gamma^+ \gamma^- \gamma^-$, which converges at high energy, the UV theory itself contributes no boundary term in eq. (32).

GAUSSIAN DIFFUSION LENS SMEARING AND POSITIVITY

Setup and kinematics

Consider a $2 \rightarrow 2$ scattering amplitude $A(s, t)$ (or helicity amplitudes $A_{\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \rightarrow \lambda_3 \lambda_4}(s, t)$). We introduce a Gaussian “diffusion lens” in momentum transfer,

$$W_\ell(q^2) \equiv e^{-\ell^2 q^2}, \quad q^2 \equiv -t \geq 0, \quad (34)$$

and study the smeared objects obtained by multiplying $A(s, t)$ with $W_\ell(q^2)$ and then performing either (i) an eikonal impact-parameter transform (high-energy/small-angle limit), or (ii) a full partial-wave (Wigner- d) decomposition at fixed s (no eikonal approximation).

In the c.m. frame, for elastic scattering with equal external masses m_{ext} ,

$$p = \sqrt{\frac{s}{4} - m_{\text{ext}}^2}, \quad t = -2p^2(1 - \cos \theta), \quad q^2 = 2p^2(1 - \cos \theta), \quad (35)$$

so that $\theta \in [0, \pi]$ corresponds to the physical region $z \equiv \cos \theta \in [-1, 1]$.

Eikonal limit: impact-parameter smearing and convolution with local EFT terms

In the eikonal regime ($s \gg |t|$), the transverse momentum transfer \vec{q} admits a 2D Fourier (Hankel) transform to impact parameter \vec{b} . Multiplying by the Gaussian lens $W_\ell(q^2)$ corresponds to a Gaussian wavepacket in \vec{b} :

$$\widetilde{W}_\ell(\vec{b}) \equiv \int \frac{d^2 \vec{q}}{(2\pi)^2} e^{i\vec{q}\vec{b}} e^{-\ell^2 q^2} = \frac{1}{4\pi\ell^2} e^{-\frac{b^2}{4\ell^2}}. \quad (36)$$

This $\mathcal{O}(G|s| \log)$ eikonal amplitude (or profile) is a convolution in \vec{b} -space.

Local EFT monomials as differential operators on $\widetilde{W}_\ell(\vec{b})$. A local EFT term proportional to $(q^2)^m$ in momentum space becomes $(-\nabla_{\vec{b}}^2)^m$ acting on $\widetilde{W}_\ell(\vec{b})$:

$$\int \frac{d^2 \vec{q}}{(2\pi)^2} e^{i\vec{q}\vec{b}} e^{-\ell^2 q^2} (q^2)^m = (-\nabla_{\vec{b}}^2)^m \widetilde{W}_\ell(\vec{b}). \quad (37)$$

In $d_\perp = 2$ dimensions, repeated Laplacians on a Gaussian admit a closed form in terms of Laguerre polynomials:

$$\left[0 \right]_{C_\infty^{\text{TP}}} \left(\nabla_{\vec{b}}^2 \right)^m \widetilde{W}_\ell(\vec{b}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\ell^2} \frac{1}{\ell^{2m}} L_m \left(\frac{b^2}{4\ell^2} \right) e^{-\frac{b^2}{4\ell^2}}. \quad (38)$$

This is the precise eikonal analogue of “derivatives of a $\delta^{(2)}(\vec{b})$ ” regulated by the diffusion lens.

Unitarity/positivity in \vec{b} -space. In an eikonal elastic regime one may write $S(s, \vec{b}) = e^{2i\delta(s, \vec{b})}$ (or include absorption via $\Im\delta \geq 0$). Unitarity implies, pointwise in \vec{b} ,

$$|S(s, \vec{b})| \leq 1, \quad P_{\text{inel}}(s, \vec{b}) \equiv 1 - |S(s, \vec{b})|^2 \geq 0, \quad (39)$$

so that for any non-negative weight $\rho(\vec{b}) \geq 0$ (e.g. $\rho = |\psi(\vec{b})|^2$ generated by W_ℓ),

$$\int d^2\vec{b} \rho(\vec{b}) [1 - |S(s, \vec{b})|^2] \geq 0. \quad (40)$$

The Gaussian lens provides a canonical, parameter-light choice of $\rho(\vec{b})$ with width $\Delta b \sim \ell$.

Full partial-wave decomposition: Wigner- d transform with a scalar lens

Away from the eikonal limit one should use the exact partial-wave basis at fixed s . For helicity amplitudes we adopt the Jacob–Wick expansion:

$$A_{mm'}(s, \theta) = 16\pi \sum_{J \geq J_{\min}} (2J+1) a_{mm'}^J(s) d_{mm'}^J(\theta), \quad (41)$$

where

$$m = \lambda_1 - \lambda_2, \quad m' = \lambda_3 - \lambda_4, \quad (42)$$

and $J_{\min} \geq \max(|m|, |m'|)$. (For scalar scattering, $m = m' = 0$ and $d_{00}^J(\theta) = P_J(\cos\theta)$.)

Scalar lens and its d_{00}^L expansion. Since W_ℓ is a scalar function of t (equivalently $z = \cos\theta$),

$$W_\ell(z) = \exp[-\ell^2 q^2(z)] = \exp[-2\rho^2 \ell^2 (1-z)] \equiv e^{-\alpha} e^{\alpha z}, \quad (43)$$

it only carries $(L, 0, 0)$ quantum numbers:

$$W_\ell(z) = \sum_{L \geq 0} (2L+1) w_L(\alpha) P_L(z) = \sum_{L \geq 0} (2L+1) w_L(\alpha) d_{00}^L(\theta), \quad (44)$$

with coefficients

$$w_L(\alpha) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 dz W_\ell(z) P_L(z) = e^{-\alpha} i_L(\alpha) > 0 \quad (\alpha > 0), \quad (45)$$

where i_L is the modified spherical Bessel function. Thus the Gaussian lens provides a canonical set of non-negative partial-wave weights $\{w_L\}$ without any multi-parameter tuning.

Smearred partial-wave coefficient with the “full kernel” $W_\ell d_{mm'}^J$. Motivated by the eikonal case (where one multiplies by W_ℓ and then projects), we define

$$\tilde{a}_{mm'}^J(s; \ell) \equiv \frac{1}{32\pi} \int_{-1}^1 dz W_\ell(z) d_{mm'}^J(\theta(z)) A_{mm'}(s, \theta(z)). \quad (46)$$

Using (41), this becomes a J -space convolution (mixing) of the original partial waves:

$$\tilde{a}_{mm'}^J(s; \ell) = \sum_{J'} (2J'+1) a_{mm'}^{J'}(s) K_{JJ'}^{mm'}(\ell), \quad K_{JJ'}^{mm'}(\ell) \equiv \frac{1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 dz \quad (47)$$

Expanding W_ℓ as (44), the kernel reduces to Clebsch–Gordan data:

$$K_{JJ'}^{mm'}(\ell) = \sum_{L \geq 0} (2L+1) w_L(\alpha) C_{J'm, L0}^{Jm} C_{J'm', L0}^{Jm'}. \quad (48)$$

In particular, for the “diagonal helicity-difference” case $m = m'$ (same in/out helicity difference),

$$K_{JJ'}^{mm}(\ell) = \sum_{L \geq 0} (2L+1) w_L(\alpha) \left(C_{J'm, L0}^{Jm} \right)^2 \geq 0, \quad (49)$$

since $w_L(\alpha) \geq 0$ and the squared CG coefficients are non-negative. This is the exact analogue of the eikonal statement that the lens induces a non-negative smearing kernel.

Positivity from s -channel unitarity. s -channel unitarity implies that for each J , the absorptive part $\Im a^J(s)$ is a positive semidefinite matrix in helicity space. Consequently, for the diagonal projection (same in/out helicity state) and for any fixed J ,

$$\Im a_{mm}^J(s) \geq 0 \quad (s \text{ on the } s\text{-cut}), \quad (50)$$

and together with (49) this yields

$$\alpha \frac{\Im \tilde{a}_{mm}^J(s; \ell)}{\Im a_{mm}^J(s)} \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } J \text{ and for any } \ell > 0, \quad (51)$$

without requiring any delicate parameter tuning of the smearing kernel.

Equivalence between the two pictures and the eikonal limit

In the large- J / small-angle regime, the Wigner- d functions reduce to Bessel functions,

$$d_{mm'}^J(\theta) \xrightarrow{J \gg 1, \theta \ll 1} (\text{phase}) \times J_{m-m'}\left(\left(J + \frac{1}{2}\right)\theta\right), \quad (52)$$

and $P_J(\cos\theta) \simeq J_0\left(\left(J + \frac{1}{2}\right)\theta\right)$ in the scalar case. Identifying the impact parameter as

$$b \simeq \frac{J + \frac{1}{2}}{p}, \quad (53)$$

the partial-wave smearing induced by W_ℓ matches the eikonal b -space Gaussian wavepacket $\tilde{W}_\ell(\vec{b})$ in (36). Therefore, the diffusion lens can be viewed equivalently as:

- a Gaussian wavepacket in impact-parameter space (eikonal regime), producing \vec{b} -space convolution and differential operators for local EFT terms, or
- a scalar d_{00}^L -weight in the full partial-wave decomposition, producing J -space convolution with non-negative CG-square kernels for diagonal helicity-difference channels.

Application to EFT constraints and the role of Wigner- d vs Legendre/Bessel

Suppose the low-energy amplitude admits an EFT expansion of the schematic form

$$A_{\text{EFT}}(s, t) = A_{\text{long}}(s, t) + \sum_{n, m} c_{nm} s^n t^m, \quad (54)$$

where A_{long} may include long-range exchanges (e.g. massless t -channel poles). One should first remove/regularize such non-analytic pieces (Born subtraction or choosing a kernel with sufficient $(1-z)^r$ suppression near $z \rightarrow 1$) so that the smeared projections are finite.

After this step, the diffusion-lens smeared partial waves $\tilde{a}_{mm}^J(s; \ell)$ can be computed from the EFT side by inserting (54) into (46). For local monomials one encounters integrals of the type

$$\int_{-1}^1 dz e^{-\alpha(1-z)} P_J(z) (1-z)^m, \quad (55)$$

which admit closed forms (e.g. in terms of derivatives of $e^{-\alpha} i_J(\alpha)$ or finite sums of incomplete Gamma functions). The UV completion then enforces positivity constraints such as (51) on the absorptive part, which can be converted into inequalities on combinations of EFT Wilson coefficients, with the lens parameter ℓ controlling the resolution scale.

Why Wigner- d is the correct basis away from eikonal. When helicities are non-trivial or when one is not parametrically in the small-angle regime, the correct orthogonal basis is the Wigner- d function. Using only P_J or J_0 outside its domain of validity would amount to an uncontrolled approximation that generally does *not* preserve exact unitarity/orthogonality properties. In contrast, the Wigner- d basis guarantees that the smearing kernel remains a scalar $(L, 0, 0)$ insertion and that the resulting J -space convolution is governed by exact CG selection rules and (for diagonal channels) manifestly non-negative CG squares. In the eikonal limit, Wigner- d reduces smoothly to the Bessel/Hankel transform picture.

INTRODUCTION

In App. we show that higher-order PM corrections do not alter the 1PM conclusion for the pure-gravity amplitude, i.e. t -pole is exactly canceled by gravitons' eikonal

ladder. In fact, once $Gs \ln(B/b) \gg 1$, where B is the size of the scattering space (IR cutoff), the scattering enters the complete absorption black disk regime. Whether it is the rapid phase oscillations of the 1PM and 2PM amplitudes or the rapid decay due to dissipative gravitational radiation at 3PM, the average discontinuity satisfies $\text{Disc } M(s, b) = 2i$ as $s \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore, the idea that 'the t -pole is exactly canceled by the 1PM ladder in dispersion relations, but receives corrections from higher-order PMs' seems not working.

In Sec. ??, we discuss how the amplitude, its discontinuity, the dispersion relations, and the EFT bound change when gravity is 'turned on' in the scattering system. We describe the effect of gravity on the amplitude by the graviton eikonal dressing: by analogy with soft dressing, which attaches soft gravitons to on-shell external lines, we attach infinitely many virtual and real gravitons of momentum $\sim 1/b$ to the approximate on-shell rails of the ladder diagrams. We show that graviton eikonal dressing **won't** induce a small negativity in the EFT bound. Moreover, removing the graviton undressing operation is not an artificial trick: one can physically realize it by changing the spatial size at which the scattering occurs.

In Sec. , we first show that, for a given gravitational theory, by varying the spatial size B of the scattering region one can achieve that 'the t -pole is canceled jointly by the eikonal ladder and by string resonances,' and we identify the dominant intervals in each case. Physically, the cancellation of the t -pole by the eikonal ladder alone occurs because the amplitude enters the black-disk regime described in App. , and unitarity bound $\text{Im } M(s, b) < 1$ forces the loop to become important and cancel the rapid growth of the tree amplitude. By contrast, the true UV completion 't-pole made of string resonances' arises when the string length $\ell_s(s)$ exceeds the spatial size B ; in that regime the strength of gravity decays exponentially (affecting both tree and loop diagrams), so that gravity is precisely canceled by the string resonances.

By a Fourier transform defined in curved space (i.e., with an IR cutoff), the strength of gravity is

$$\delta_0^{\text{string}}(s+i\epsilon, b, B) = Gs \begin{cases} \log\left(\frac{B^2}{b^2}\right) - \frac{Y_c}{b^2} \exp\left(-\frac{b^2}{Y_c}\right), & \sqrt{\alpha'} \ll \ell_s(s) \\ \log\left(\frac{B^2}{Y_c}\right), & b \ll \ell_s(s) \\ \frac{B^2}{Y_c} \exp\left(-\frac{Y_c}{B^2}\right), & B \ll \ell_s(s). \end{cases} \quad (56)$$

where $Y_c = \alpha' \log(-i\alpha' s) = l_s^2 - i\pi\alpha'$. We observe that when $\sqrt{\alpha'} \ll \ell_s(s) \ll B$, the discontinuity of the amplitude is independent of the IR cutoff B . However, when $B \ll \ell_s(s)$, the discontinuity, i.e. the UV spectrum, does

depend on B :

$$\text{Im } \delta_0^{\text{string}}(s, b, B) = G_s \begin{cases} \frac{\pi\alpha'}{l_s^2} \exp\left(-\frac{b^2}{l_s^2}\right), & 1 \ll \ell_s(s) \ll b, \\ \frac{\pi\alpha'}{l_s^2}, & b \ll \ell_s(s) \ll B, \\ \frac{\pi\alpha'}{l_s^2} \exp\left(-\frac{l_s^2}{B^2}\right), & B \ll \ell_s(s). \end{cases} \quad (57)$$

The two exponential factors above strongly suggest the geometric interpretation of gravity. We will further argue that for any UV completion of the graviton, the UV spectrum must be suppressed by a UV cutoff induced by the spatial size B .

When $B \lesssim \ell_s(M_p^2)$ [19], string resonances dominate the cancellation of the t -pole. At that point, the residue at $s = 0$, $G \log(B/b)$, is IR-dependent. If the UV resonances arise from a model insensitive to B , then as B decreases the t -pole is over-canceled by UV resonances into a repulsive gravity. The corresponding eikonal loop of repulsion produces a negative imaginary part of the amplitude, thus violating unitarity. Hence any UV completion of gravity should have a string-like spatial compactification, otherwise one cannot explain the disappearance of gravity when $\ell_s(s) \gtrsim B$ (analogous to asymptotic freedom in QCD).

In Sec. ?? we return to our original goal of bootstrapping QCD (or generally QFT). The twice-subtracted dispersion relation (2SDR) for $h^+h^+h^-h^-$ scattering reads

$$-\frac{G}{t} + \text{else?} = G\langle\text{string}\rangle + G^2\langle\text{QCD}\rangle - \text{boundary?}$$

where we have removed the graviton eikonal dressing on $\langle\text{QCD}\rangle$, and made the t -pole mainly canceled by $\langle\text{string}\rangle$ by controlling B . A key question is: who accounts for $\langle\text{QCD}\rangle$? There are only three possibilities:

a. The t -pole is not completely canceled by string resonances; the leftover part is canceled by QCD.

- However, if one considers simultaneously $h^+h^+h^-h^-$, $h^+\gamma^+h^-\gamma^-$, and $h^+\pi h^-\pi$ scattering, their QCD contributions scale as G^2 , Ge^2 , and Gf_π^{-2} , respectively. One cannot expect a same leftover term $\sim G$ to cancel three different things.

b. QCD induces a nonzero boundary term.

- A nonzero boundary contradicts the Froissart bound and Regge behavior[20], and furthermore such a boundary would lead to repulsive gravity as $s \rightarrow \infty$, whose loops would violate unitarity.

c. There is some else contribution at $s = 0$ that we missed.

- Our low-energy expansions have always been based on simple poles from resonances, but in fact QCD-induced $h^+h^+h^-h^-$ scattering must include the Pomeron, which represents the combined effect of infinitely many branch cuts. This does not forbid low-energy ‘else?’ terms.

When the t -channel carries vacuum quantum numbers, the Pomeron necessarily propagates and in large- N QCD it is the leading $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ contribution. The Pomeron corresponds to glueball exchange: in the large- N topological representation, four gravitons connect to a closed S^2 sphere, and one can fix the singularities of this amplitude uniquely by the Veneziano–Shapiro form. Unlike local EFT resonances, which enforce all operators to scale as $[12]^4\langle 34 \rangle^4 \sim s^4$, the Pomeron allows an s^2 low-energy EFT.

The differences between the QCD ($\alpha_0 \approx 1$, 1.1 GeV) and the gravitational closed string ($\alpha_0 = 2$, M_s) are just the intercept and slope of their Regge trajectories $\alpha(t)$, otherwise they share similar properties. Closed strings have only a single parent trajectory and do not require infinitely many daughter trajectories as open strings do; once $\alpha(t)$ is specified, the amplitude is determined by very few parameters. Essentially, the Pomeron is not a simple pole like a Reggeon but an infinite superposition of cuts that behaves like a pole.

We conclude that the anomaly or R^3 couplings are not bounded by $G \log(B/b)$. We can fully separate the contributions of Quantum Gravity (QG) and QCD: the t -pole is canceled by closed-string resonances at scale M_s and by eikonal loops; while the t -channel Pomeron, which gives an s^2 EFT, is canceled by closed or open (depending on the process) QCD string resonances at scale 1.1 GeV (entirely distinct from QG string at M_s). In this way, R^3 (anomaly) coupling constraints become independent of G and are purely QCD bounds

$$|\beta_{R^3}| \leq \frac{\log(m_{\text{HS}}/\Lambda_{\text{IR}})}{m_{\text{HS}}^4} \Rightarrow |\beta_{R^3}| \leq \frac{G}{m_{\text{HS}}^2} c.$$

where c is the EFT coefficient of s^2 induced by t -channel Pomeron, and $\beta_{R^3} \equiv G\kappa_3/\Lambda^2$ in [21].

BOOTSTRAP QUANTUM GRAVITY

Compared to the toy model, we are now interested in the UV completions of gravity. We will control the space size B and the integral contour $C_{|s|}$ to optimally bootstrap the amplitude.

UV completions of Gravity: Closed String

At tree level, the Veneziano amplitude packages the graviton and an infinite tower of string resonances onto

the same Regge trajectory, giving a vanishing 2DR boundary. As [22] showed, the dominant string-resonance contribution comes from the region

$$\frac{\alpha' \ln(\alpha' s_*)}{b^2} \equiv \frac{\ell_s^2(s_*)}{b^2} \sim \mathcal{O}(1). \quad (58)$$

and preserving unitarity at s_* requires $G s_* \ll 1$, i.e. $b \ll \ell_s(G^{-1})$. One might conclude that whenever α' and G differ by many orders of magnitude, string resonances alone can cancel the t -pole. However, tree-level approximation not only requires the tree-level string correction $\ll 1$, but also demands that the tree-level graviton phase satisfy

$$G s_* \log(1/b\Lambda_{\text{IR}}) \ll 1, \quad (59)$$

which fails as $\Lambda_{\text{IR}} \rightarrow 0$. Hence, for any impact parameter b , whether large or small compared to $\ell_s(s)$, gravitational ladder diagrams remain essential in flat 4D space.

As we will see, the calculation then mirrors our analysis of $\Delta\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}$ in Sec. : the eikonal ladder diagrams of gravity itself still cancel the t -pole, with the **dressed tree-level string resonances** and their **ripples** precisely canceling each other. Thus, even when the graviton is Reggeized into string excitations, in flat 4D spacetime the graviton eikonal ladder still dominates the cancellation of t -pole.

Motivated by this, we place the scattering in a finite space to undress the graviton loops and expose the string resonances, in order to bootstrap the UV completion of gravity. Using the Fourier transform of closed string amplitude [12], we will see that the dominant contribution to the 2DR from string theory comes from resonances with mass m such that $b \lesssim \ell_s(m^2) \lesssim B$. To prevent these resonances from being washed out by loops, we require $B \lesssim \ell_s(G^{-1})$. In summary,

$$t\text{-pole} = \begin{cases} \text{Graviton ladder diagrams,} & \ell_s[1/G \log(B/b)] \lesssim b, \\ \text{Mixed,} & \text{middle,} \\ \text{String resonances with UV cutoff,} & B \lesssim \ell_s(G^{-1}) \end{cases} \quad (60)$$

When $\delta_0^{\text{string}}(m^2) \gtrsim 1$, the contour integral rapidly goes to 0 due to the oscillation described in App. , i.e. by the ladder diagrams. This reflects entry into the black disk regime rather than a genuine UV completion of gravity. By contrast, tree-level t -pole is indeed made of string resonances in $b \lesssim \ell_s(m^2) \lesssim B$. Since all resonances with $\delta_0^{\text{string}}(m^2) \gtrsim 1$ are washed out by their own loop effects, and the intervals in eq. (60) are just $\delta_0^{\text{string}}|_{\ell_s=b} \lesssim 1$ and $\delta_0^{\text{string}}|_{\ell_s=B} \gtrsim 1$, respectively.

By choosing the space radius B such that the amplitude falls into the last regime, we find that the IR cutoff B imposes a UV cutoff on any UV completion of graviton. This is because the t -pole becomes $G \log(B/b)$ after Fourier transforming in finite space. If we demand that

the UV theory of gravity satisfies $M(s, t) \sim s^{2-\epsilon}$ at tree level, then

$$G \log(B/b) = \int_0^{G^{-1}} \frac{ds}{s^2} \text{Disc} \quad (61)$$

implies that the discontinuity must depend on B , establishing an IR–UV connection. And only geometric interpretations like string theory, where resonances arise from compactification of extra dimensions, can naturally explain why the UV spectrum is sensitive to IR scales.

String in Flat Space: Can we neglect graviton loops?

In the limit $s \gg \max(t, 1/\alpha')$, the tree-level scattering amplitude of dilatons in type II string theory is given by

$$M_0(s + i\epsilon, t) \simeq \frac{32\pi G}{\alpha'} \frac{\Gamma(-\frac{\alpha'}{4}t)}{\Gamma(1 + \frac{\alpha'}{4}t)} \left(\frac{\alpha'}{4}s\right)^{2 + \frac{\alpha'}{2}t} e^{-i\pi\frac{\alpha'}{4}t}. \quad (62)$$

however, we care about the t -pole, which is provided only by $\Gamma(-\alpha't/4)$ in the regime $\alpha't \ll 1$, and the amplitude becomes

$$M_0(s + i\epsilon, t) \simeq \frac{8\pi G s^2}{-t} e^{\frac{\alpha'}{2}t [\log(\frac{\alpha' s}{4}) - \frac{i\pi}{2}]}. \quad (63)$$

You applied the 2DR to the tree-level amplitude in momentum-space, where the low-energy contour C_0 and the positive discontinuity integral are respectively

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{C_0} \frac{ds}{s^3} M_0 &\simeq (2\pi i) \frac{8\pi G}{-t}, \\ 2 \int_{4/\alpha'}^{\infty} \frac{ds}{s^3} \text{Disc } M_0 &\simeq \int_{4/\alpha'}^{\infty} \frac{ds}{s^3} \left[8\pi G s^2 \cdot \alpha' e^{\frac{\alpha'}{2}t \log(\frac{\alpha' s}{4})} \right] = (2\pi i) \frac{8\pi G}{-t} \int_{4/\alpha'}^{\infty} \frac{ds}{s} \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

with $x = -t \ell_s^2(s)$. This gives your elegant conclusion that the tree-level graviton made of string resonances. Since the Integral is dominated by $x \sim \mathcal{O}(1)$, the tree-level approximation must hold throughout this region. Equivalently, when $\ell_s(s) \sim b$, all loop corrections should remain much smaller than the tree amplitude. The simplest check is to compute the eikonal loop amplitude and verify that loops are indeed subleading. The mixed massless graviton and massive resonances ladder diagrams of eq. (6) then give

$$\begin{aligned} 1 + i\mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{string}}(s + i\epsilon, b) &= \exp \left[iGs \left(\log(1/b^2 \Lambda_{\text{IR}}^2) - \int_{\frac{b^2}{Y_c}}^{\infty} \frac{dt}{t} e^{-t} \right) \right] \\ &= \exp \left[i\delta_0 - iGs E_1 \left(\frac{b^2}{Y_c} \right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

where $Y_c = 2\alpha' \log(\frac{-i\alpha' s}{4})$ [23]. Substituting $\ell_s(s_*) \sim b$ gives the Exponential Integral $E_1 \sim \mathcal{O}(1)$, so resonance-loop corrections are negligible if $G s_* \ll 1$. Together with

$\alpha't \ll 1$, this restricts the impact parameter to

$$\alpha' \ll b^2 \ll \ell_s^2(G^{-1}). \quad (66)$$

However, we must also include graviton-loop corrections, which require $Gs_* \log(1/b\Lambda_{\text{IR}}) \ll 1$, a condition that cannot be met in flat space. Here we compare the string-tree amplitude above, with the graviton string-loop amplitude appropriate for $|s| \lesssim s_*$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{string-tree}}(s+i\epsilon, b) &= \delta_0 - Gs E_1\left(\frac{b^2/\alpha'}{\log(-i\alpha's)}\right) \\ \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{string-loop}}(s+i\epsilon, b) &= i(1 - e^{i\delta_0}) - e^{i\delta_0} \cdot Gs E_1\left(\frac{b^2/\alpha'}{\log(-i\alpha's)}\right) \frac{1}{2\pi i} \oint_{C_{|s|}} \frac{ds}{s^2} \delta_0^{\text{string}}(s, b, B) \end{aligned} \quad (67)$$

In Feynman-diagram form:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{string-tree}} &= \text{[Diagram 1]} + \text{[Diagram 2]} \\ \mathcal{M}_{\text{eik}}^{\text{string-loop}} &= \text{[Diagram 3]} + \text{[Diagram 4]} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (68)$$

For the string-tree amplitude, the t -pole in the first diagram is canceled by the string resonances in the second. For the dressed string-tree amplitude, the graviton t -pole and loops cut cancel within the first diagram, while the **dressed resonances** in the second is canceled by its **ripples**. In other words, even for b in the window of eq. (66), graviton loops will still come in and *cancel* the t -pole, preventing us from seeing what it is *made of*.

String in Curved Space: UV completion of gravity

Above we saw that graviton loops in flat 4D space are not negligible, the graviton t -pole is always canceled by eikonal ladder diagrams. However, once the scattering is placed in a spacetime with curvature radius B , string theory naturally provides a UV cutoff when the scattering energy grows such that $\ell_s(s) \sim B$. A consistent theory of quantum gravity seems required to exhibit this IR-induced UV cutoff, which imposes a remarkably strong constraint.

All previous amplitudes in b -space were derived in flat D -dimensional spacetime, with the IR cutoff B introduced when taking $D \rightarrow 4$. However, if B does not go to infinity, we cannot directly apply the result of [12]. Here, we instead perform the Fourier transform of eq. (63) directly in a finite space of size B , and obtain the dependence of the amplitude \mathcal{M} , as well as the $C_{|s|}$ contour integral over a disk of radius $|s|$ in the complex s -plane, on B .

In the eikonal limit $s \gg 1/\alpha' \gg t$, the tree-level am-

plitude and its contour integral in momentum space is

$$\begin{aligned} M_0(s+i\epsilon, -q^2) &= \frac{8\pi Gs^2}{q^2} e^{-q^2 Y_c} \\ \frac{1}{2\pi i} \oint_{C_{|s|}} \frac{ds}{s^3} M_0(s, -q^2) &= \frac{8\pi G}{q^2} e^{-q^2 l_s^2} \end{aligned} \quad (69)$$

Perform the Fourier transform and exchange the order of integral $\int ds$ and $\int dq$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_0^{\text{string}}(s+i\epsilon, b, B) &= \int_{1/B^2}^{\infty} d(q^2) J_0(bq) \frac{Gs}{q^2} e^{-q^2 Y_c} \\ \frac{1}{2\pi i} \oint_{C_{|s|}} \frac{ds}{s^2} \delta_0^{\text{string}}(s, b, B) &= \int_{1/B^2}^{\infty} d(q^2) J_0(bq) \frac{G}{q^2} e^{-q^2 l_s^2} \end{aligned} \quad (70)$$

By analytic continuation, we find that the tree-level string amplitude has approximation

$$\mathcal{M}^{\text{string}}(s+i\epsilon, b, B) = Gs \begin{cases} \log\left(\frac{B^2}{b^2}\right) - \frac{Y_c}{b^2} \exp\left(-\frac{b^2}{Y_c}\right), & \sqrt{\alpha'} \ll \ell_s \\ \log\left(\frac{B^2}{Y_c}\right), & b \ll \ell_s(s) \\ \frac{B^2}{Y_c} \exp\left(-\frac{Y_c}{B^2}\right), & B \ll \ell_s(s) \end{cases} \quad (71)$$

and its $C_{|s|}$ contour integral have an entirely analogous form,

$$\oint_{C_{|s|}} \frac{ds}{s^2} \mathcal{M}^{\text{string}}(s, b, B) = G \begin{cases} \log\left(\frac{B^2}{b^2}\right) - \frac{l_s^2}{b^2} \exp\left(-\frac{b^2}{l_s^2}\right), & \sqrt{\alpha'} \ll \ell_s \\ \log\left(\frac{B^2}{l_s^2}\right), & b \ll \ell_s \\ \frac{B^2}{l_s^2} \exp\left(-\frac{l_s^2}{B^2}\right), & B \ll \ell_s \end{cases} \quad (72)$$

The only difference is that when $\delta_0^{\text{string}} \gtrsim 1$, the ladder loop amplitude need be obtained by exponentiating the tree-level result. However when $G|s| \gg 1$, the ladder diagrams wash out the string resonances through the **dressed resonances** and **ripples** mechanisms, and strongly suppressing the $C_{|s|}$ contour integral. To bootstrap quantum gravity, we choose the impact parameter b and IR cutoff B such that $\sqrt{\alpha'} \ll b \ll B \ll \ell_s(G^{-1})$.

We see that the dominant contribution from string resonances to the 2DR comes from the region $b \lesssim \ell_s(s) \lesssim B$. When ℓ_s exceeds the spacetime size B , the amplitude behaves as $\mathcal{M}(s, b) \sim s^{1-\alpha'/B^2}$, which satisfies the high-energy behavior in b -space. However, varying B within the range $b \ll B \ll \ell_s(G^{-1})$ change the IR-dependent t -pole, $G \log(B/b)$, which is canceled by string resonances. This implies that the mass spectrum of string resonances is sensitive to the size of spacetime—an insight that likely extends to general quantum gravity.

String amplitudes indeed support this picture. When $B \ll \ell_s(G^{-1})$, the amplitude can be approximated by its tree-level diagram across all three regions below. In

FIG. 2. The contour integral of eq. (72) for parameters $B : b : \sqrt{\alpha'} : \sqrt{G} = 50 : 5 : 1 : 10^{-8}$, illustrating the t -pole cancellation. The blue curve shows that the Reggeized graviton tree-level amplitude is mainly canceled by resonances in $b \lesssim \ell_s(s) \lesssim B$, while the orange curve shows the rapid drop of the $C_{|s|}$ integral once $\delta_0^{\text{string}} \gtrsim 1$ enters the black-disk regime, which occurs at $s \sim G^{-1}$. The green plateau region allows us to isolate the QFT from quantum gravity in Sec. ??.

particular, the discontinuity in the last regime effectively implements a UV cutoff at $s_{\text{UV}} \sim M_s^2 e^{B^2 M_s^2}$,

$$\frac{1}{G_s} \cdot \text{Im} \mathcal{M}^{\text{string}}(s, b, B) = \begin{cases} \frac{\pi \alpha'}{l_s^2} \exp\left(-\frac{b^2}{l_s^2}\right), & 1 \ll \ell_s(s) \ll b \\ \frac{\pi \alpha'}{l_s^2}, & b \ll \ell_s(s) \ll B \\ \frac{\pi \alpha'}{l_s^2} \exp\left(-\frac{l_s^2}{B^2}\right), & B \ll \ell_s(s) \ll \frac{b}{G} \end{cases} \quad (73)$$

Moreover, the upper regime $\ell_s \ll b$ and the lower regime $B \ll \ell_s$ are in fact dual to each other, vary possible to hint some deeper underlying physics.

To summarize, we show the contour integral of the full ladder amplitude in Fig. 2, which is given by the lower of the two curves. When $\ell_s(s) \ll b$, the residue is unchanged; For $b \lesssim \ell_s(s) \lesssim \ell_s(G^{-1})$, string resonances take over the cancellation; Once $s \gtrsim G^{-1}$, it is the ladder of gravitons and string resonances as in eq. (6) that cancels the pole. To have the t -pole dominated by string resonances requires $b^2/\alpha' \rightarrow 1$ or $G/\alpha' \rightarrow 0$, i.e. probing extremely short distances or an extremely weak gravity. In most cases, ladders *cancel* the t -pole, but this does not mean the t -pole is *made of* it. We think gravitons and string resonances to be different excitation modes of the same closed string, interdependent, and that when $B \lesssim \ell_s(s)$, the closed-string interactions, i.e. the Reggeized gravity, vanish.

IR-CANCELLATION IN PURE GRAVITY

1PM: Results from Julio and You

In Momentum-Space: Consider the $2 \rightarrow 2$ scattering amplitude (which may be massless or massive, no difference in the 1PM). Following Veneziano, the momentum-

space amplitude is

$$M(s + i\epsilon, -q^2) \simeq \frac{8\pi G s^2}{q^2} \exp\left(i 2Gs \log \frac{q}{\Lambda_{\text{IR}}}\right), \quad (74)$$

and we got the discontinuity

$$\text{Disc}(s, q) \simeq i \frac{8\pi G s^2}{q^2} 2 \sin\left(2Gs \log \frac{q}{\Lambda_{\text{IR}}}\right). \quad (75)$$

Then the 2DR is

$$\oint_{C_0} \frac{ds}{s^3} M(s, -q^2) = 2 \left(\int_0^{\Lambda^2} ds + \int_{\Lambda^2}^{\infty} ds \right) \frac{1}{s^3} \text{Disc} M(s, -q^2) \xrightarrow{\text{FT/smearing}} 8\pi G \log(1/b\Lambda_{\text{IR}}) = \left(8\pi G \log(1/b\Lambda_{\text{IR}}) - \frac{8}{\Lambda^2} \right) + \frac{8}{\Lambda^2} \quad (76)$$

This is Julio's interesting result. We see that, at 1PM, using a unitary cut to construct the discontinuity, the two-particle cut (2pc) cancels the IR cutoff. However, one may ask why the s -integral should be truncated at Λ^2 . In Julio's model, additional interactions (large- N , string, ...) have already been added to the Lagrangian, so the discontinuity above the lightest resonance is not purely gravity, but rather a positive mixture of gravity and UV resonances. What Julio is actually bounding is this mixed contribution, which explains why the bound is weak.

However, in a pure gravity model, there seems to be nothing but black holes to stop the s -integral. Can black holes truly cancel the IR cutoff while leaving a nonzero contribution? In fact, they cannot.

In Position-Space: We now turn to the impact parameter space, where the analysis becomes even clearer. The amplitude is given by

$$M(s+i\epsilon, b) = i \left[1 - S(s+i\epsilon, b) \right] = i \left[1 - \exp\left(i 2Gs \log(1/b\Lambda_{\text{IR}})\right) \right]. \quad (77)$$

And we got the discontinuity

$$\text{Disc}(s, b) = 2i \left[1 - \cos\left(2Gs \log(1/b\Lambda_{\text{IR}})\right) \right]. \quad (78)$$

the dispersion relation becomes

$$\oint_{C_0} ds \frac{1}{s^2} M(s, b) = 2 \left(\int_0^{\Lambda^2} ds + \int_{\Lambda^2}^{\infty} ds \right) \frac{1}{s^2} \text{Disc} M(s, b) \xrightarrow{\text{calc}} 2G \log(1/b\Lambda_{\text{IR}}) = \frac{1}{\Lambda^2} \left(a - \frac{2}{\pi} - \frac{\sin a}{a} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{a^2}\right) \right) + \frac{1}{\Lambda^2} \left(\frac{2}{\pi} + \frac{\sin a}{a} \right) \quad (79)$$

where $a \equiv 2G\Lambda^2 \log(1/b\Lambda_{\text{IR}})$. As $\Lambda_{\text{IR}} \rightarrow 0$, all terms have $1/a \sim 1/\log \Lambda_{\text{IR}}$ are suppressed. Combining the two integration regions yields your elegant result. We separate them for two reasons: 1. To introduce black hole later; 2. The IR-divergent residue at $s = 0$ is actually canceled by the discontinuity in its neighborhood, meaning all singular contributions within the interval $(-\Lambda^2, \Lambda^2)$ are IR-independent.

Collapse to Black Hole

Eardley and Giddings pointed out that in the black hole formation region, when

$$\frac{G\sqrt{s}}{b} > \frac{1}{\gamma_{EG}} \simeq 0.62, \quad (80)$$

the produced black hole decays (e.g., via Hawking radiation) into a completely different final state, so we treat it as fully inelastic, i.e.

$$\text{Disc}_{BH}(s, b) = 2i. \quad (81)$$

This implies that, at 1PM order, the t -pole is completely canceled by the two-particle cut and the black hole channel. Since in the integration region $\int_{\Lambda^2}^{\infty}$ of Eq. (79), within the discontinuity $(1 - \cos a)$, only the 1 contributes while the $\cos a$ contribution is infinitely suppressed. A natural follow-up question is whether intermediate states involving the two original particles along with hard/soft gravitons (gravitational radiation) might alter this conclusion?

2PM: Elastic Cut

The 2PM eikonal phase is purely real, which means the scattering remains fully elastic, i.e. the intermediate state in the unitarity cut is still just the two-particle state. For particle scattering with mass m , the PM approximation is only valid in the regime $s \gg m^2 \gg t$, so we do not know what happens inside the neighborhood $(-m^2, m^2)$. However, we can bypass this ambiguity using analyticity. This ambiguous region appears whether we are studying massive or massless particle scattering. For massless scattering, the discontinuity in the region $(t, -t)$ is likewise unknown, and the method described below applies to both cases.

We begin by writing the expression for δ_1 in the ultra-relativistic limit:

$$\delta_1 = \frac{6}{\pi} \frac{G^2 s}{b^2} \log \frac{s}{m^2}. \quad (82)$$

This formula is only valid away from the region $(-m^2, m^2)$. However, since we only need to calculate the IR-independent part, we can completely deform the dispersion relation as

$$\oint_{C_{11}} ds \frac{1}{s^2} M(s, b) = \oint_{C_0} ds \frac{1}{s^2} M(s, b) - 2 \int_0^{\Lambda^2} ds \frac{1}{s^2} \text{Disc} M(s, b) \quad (83)$$

where we retain the integral $\int_{\Lambda^2}^{\infty}$ so that the entire contour C_{11} can be described by PM amplitude without encountering the black hole region, later we will push Λ^2 to the critical point to form black hole at $G^{-2}b^2$. If the contributions from C_{11} and $\int_{\Lambda^2}^{\infty}$ cancel each other, it means

FIG. 3. Bypass the ambiguous region by deforming the integration contour

that the t -pole at 2PM is completely canceled, leaving no nonzero and IR-independent contribution as we wanted. The integral over the contour C_{11} is

$$\oint_{C_{11}} ds \frac{1}{s^2} M(s, b) = 4 \text{Re} \left[\int_{\Lambda^2+i\epsilon}^{\Lambda^2+i\infty} \frac{ds}{s^2} i \left[1 - \exp\left(ia \frac{s}{\Lambda^2} + i \frac{12}{\pi} \frac{G^2 s}{b^2} \log \frac{s}{m_1 m_2}\right) \right] \right] \quad (84)$$

Similar to eq. (79), all terms proportional to a^{-1} are suppressed by a factor of $1/\log \Lambda_{\text{IR}}$. If the integrand can be factorized into a rapidly oscillating (decaying) and a slowly varying function, then the Stationary Phase Method can be used to approximate the integral, and in the limit $\Lambda_{\text{IR}} \rightarrow 10$ the approximation becomes exact[24]. Now the integral over C_{11} is

$$\oint_{C_{11}} \frac{ds}{s^2} M(s, b) = 4i \text{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\Lambda^2} - \frac{1}{a \Lambda^2} i \left[\exp\left(ia + i \frac{12}{\pi} \frac{G^2 \Lambda^2}{b^2} \log \frac{\Lambda^2}{m_1 m_2}\right) \right] \right] \quad (85)$$

We let $\Lambda^2 = G^{-2}b^2$, unfortunately, the contributions

from $\int_{\Lambda^2}^{\infty}$ and $C_{||}$ still cancel each other,

$$\oint_{C_{||}}^{\Lambda=b/G} \frac{ds}{s^2} M(s, b) = \frac{4i}{\Lambda^2} \Big|_{\Lambda=b/G} = 2 \int_{\Lambda^2=b^2/G^2}^{\infty} \frac{ds}{s^2} \text{Disc}_{BH}. \quad (86)$$

2PM serves as our toy model before entering 3PM, it shows that real eikonal phase which isn't proportional to $\log \Lambda_{\text{IR}}$ does not affect the cancellation of the t -pole. Thus, the question now is, at 3PM we introduce an extra imaginary eikonal dissipation, will it affect?

3PM: Elastic and Inelastic Cut

3PM corresponds to the exponentiation of the 5-point gravitational tree amplitude in the eikonal limit, with normal ordering applied to the graviton creation and annihilation operators. Now both soft and hard gravitons are radiated, and the intermediate state is no longer restricted to the elastic two-particle cut but can include an infinite number of gravitons. So for elastic scattering, 3PM phase has a real phase shift and also an imaginary dissipation. Let us first see, via the optical theorem, how the inelastic channels affect the discontinuity.

It should be clarified that the $|\text{in}\rangle$ and $|\text{out}\rangle$ states in eikonal scattering are both described by $|s, b\rangle$ in position space, differing only by the phase shift δ_{PM} . And the deflection angle in momentum space is just given by $\Theta \sim \partial\delta_{PM}/\partial b\sqrt{s}$. So the discontinuity is essentially equivalent to the cross section.

Consider an elastic scattering that has both phase shift and dissipation. Its amplitude is

$$\langle s, b|T|s, b\rangle = i\left(1 - e^{i2\delta - 2\Delta}\right). \quad (87)$$

The total discontinuity, as well as the contribution to the discontinuity from the elastic cut, is given by

$$\begin{aligned} -i\langle s, b|T - T^\dagger|s, b\rangle &= 2\left(1 - e^{-2\Delta} \cos(2\delta)\right), \\ \langle s, b|T^\dagger|s, b\rangle\langle s, b|T|s, b\rangle &= \left(1 - e^{-i2\delta - 2\Delta}\right)\left(1 - e^{i2\delta - 2\Delta}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (88)$$

Thus, the contribution from inelastic cut to discontinuity is[25]

$$\begin{aligned} \langle s, b|T^\dagger|\text{else}\rangle\langle\text{else}|T|s, b\rangle &= \left(-i\langle s, b|T - T^\dagger|s, b\rangle\right) - \left(\langle s, b|T^\dagger|s, b\rangle\langle s, b|T|s, b\rangle\right), \\ &= 1 - e^{-4\Delta} \end{aligned} \quad (89)$$

Next, we consider whether each term in the 3PM phase δ_2 gives nonzero corrections when combined with δ_0 . We ignore cross terms between δ_2 and δ_1 , as they are further suppressed by powers of $1/\log \Lambda_{\text{IR}}$. In the ultra-relativistic limit, the 3PM phase takes the form:

$$\delta_2 = \frac{2G^3 s^2}{b^2} \left(i \frac{2 \log(s/m^2)}{\pi} \left(\log \frac{1}{b\Lambda_{\text{IR}}} + 1 \right) + 1 \right). \quad (90)$$

FIG. 4. **1PM and 2PM**: Eikonal phase is purely real so that Disc is a rapidly oscillating function. **3PM (only hard)**: Now the eikonal phase includes both a phase shift and an IR-finite dissipation, causing the oscillations in Disc to be damped. **2pc in 3PM** and **(2+n)-pc in 3PM** indicate the contributions from the 2-particle channel and the n-particle channel, respectively.

IR-finite: phase shift + hard dissipation

First, we consider the IR-finite pieces of δ_2 , whose real part contributes to the deflection angle and imaginary part corresponds to the emission and absorption of hard gravitons. The contribution of the intermediate states to the discontinuity is given by

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int d(\text{LIPS})_n \langle s, b|T^\dagger|s', b'; h_1, \dots, h_n\rangle \langle s', b'; h_1, \dots, h_n|T|s, b\rangle. \quad (91)$$

Here, we compare the cases of considering only the 2-particle cut (1PM, 2PM) versus including the n-particle cut (3PM, only hard). 1. the dissipation effectively damps the oscillations proportional to $\log \Lambda_{\text{IR}}$. But Disc is should be an IR-independent observable quantity[26]; 2. if we separate Disc into contributions from the elastic and inelastic channels, the inelastic contribution is completely IR independent.

Since the total GR contribution to the discontinuity is clear, we proceed to check whether the t -pole is exactly canceled. Using the stationary phase method, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \oint_{C_{||}} \frac{ds}{s^2} M(s, b) &= 4 \text{Re} \left[\int_{\Lambda^2+i\epsilon}^{\Lambda^2+i\infty} \frac{ds}{s^2} i \left[1 - \exp\left(ia \frac{s}{\Lambda^2} + i \frac{4G^3 s^2}{b^2} \frac{2i \log(\Lambda^2/m^2)}{\pi}\right) \right] \right] \\ &= 4i \text{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\Lambda^2} - \frac{1}{a\Lambda^2} i \left[\exp\left(ia + i \frac{4G^3 \Lambda^4}{b^2} \frac{2i \log(\Lambda^2/m^2)}{\pi}\right) \right] \right] \end{aligned} \quad (92)$$

According to eq. (86), the t -pole is still exactly canceled, as all uncanceled terms are suppressed by $1/\log \Lambda_{\text{IR}}$.

IR-divergent: soft dissipation

Intuitively, the Λ_{IR} arises when the t-channel graviton becomes very soft, so to resolve this issue we should study the effect of soft gravitons on both the amplitude and its discontinuity.

Finite numbers of soft particles in the external states yield IR-divergent amplitudes. We need to resum and

FIG. 5. Schematic of soft summation (Copy from Recardo).

integrate over the phase space of the soft particles in the initial and final states, to obtain IR-independent observables such as cross sections and discontinuities. First, we need to show that eq. (91) still holds when soft particles are involved:

$$\begin{aligned} & -i \langle s, b; 0 | T - T^\dagger | s, b; 0 \rangle \\ &= \sum_{m,n=1}^{\infty} \int_{\text{soft}} d(\text{LIPS})_{m,n} \langle s, b; h_1, \dots, h_m | T^\dagger | s', b'; h_1, \dots, h_n \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (93)$$

Above equation differs slightly from eq. (91). However, because m incoming soft gravitons can attach to a Feynman diagram only via annihilation operators while n outgoing soft gravitons attach only via creation operators, the on-shell (i.e. δ -function) soft gravitons can be effectively reassembled into the propagator connecting M and M^* in Fig. 5,

$$\frac{1}{p^2 + i\epsilon} = -(2\pi i) \delta(p^2) = -i \frac{\pi}{|p|} \left[\delta(p_0 - |p|) + \delta(p_0 + |p|) \right]. \quad (94)$$

Thus, eq. (93) is also valid.

Now we need to compute the scattering between the states $|s, b; 0\rangle$, which has no soft gravitons in the initial or final state. This amplitude can be obtained directly by substituting into the operator form of Veneziano's 3PM S-matrix:

$$\hat{S} = e^{2i(\delta_0 + \delta_1 + \delta_2)} : \exp \left[\sqrt{2} i g^3 s \int \frac{d\mathbf{q}_1}{(2\pi)^2} e^{i\mathbf{b}\cdot\mathbf{q}_1} \int \frac{d^3q}{2\omega_q} \frac{\Theta(q_1 - q)}{(2\pi)^3} \oint_{C_{||}} \frac{\sin \theta_{sq}}{|\mathbf{q}|^2} \left(\hat{A}_q(\hat{a}, \hat{b}) \hat{A}_q^\dagger(\hat{a}, \hat{b}) \right) \right]_{\text{PM}} = 4i \frac{1}{\Lambda^2} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\log(b\Lambda_{\text{IR}})}\right). \quad (95)$$

where \hat{A}_q (\hat{A}_q^\dagger) are the absorption (emission) operators for soft gravitons. The normal ordering indicated by the colons $:\dots:$ ensures that the scattering amplitude between the states $|s, b; 0\rangle$ does not involve any contributions from the radiation operators. Accordingly, we have the Disc when soft radiation took into account

$$\langle s + i\epsilon, b; 0 | \hat{T} | s + i\epsilon, b; 0 \rangle = i \left[1 - e^{2i(\delta_0 + \delta_1 + \delta_2)} \right]. \quad (96)$$

Inserting this into eq. (93), we obtain the discontinuity

$$\text{Disc} = \langle s, b; 0 | \hat{T} - \hat{T}^\dagger | s, b; 0 \rangle = 2i \left[1 - e^{-2\text{Im}[\delta]} \cos(2\text{Re}[\delta]) \right]. \quad (97)$$

The $\text{Im}[\delta]$ receives contributions from the IR-divergent soft dissipation at 3PM, which forces $\text{Disc} \rightarrow 2i$ quickly.

FIG. 6. 1PM and 2PM: Disc is rapidly oscillatory. Complete 3PM (hard + soft): The IR-divergent soft dissipation now dominates, so the oscillations in Disc decay rapidly. 2pc in complete 3PM and (2+n)-pc in complete 3PM have $\text{Disc} = 1$, except neighborhood of $s = 0$.

That is, the scattering is fully inelastic because there is always some soft radiation in the final state, even if the initial state contains only hard particles.

Fig. 6 shows the Disc for each channel. Compared with the rapidly oscillating Disc at 1PM, the rapid damping induced by soft dissipation makes the $\text{Disc} = 2i$ at any finite s . This is consistent with our previous understanding that Disc is an IR-independent observable[27].

Now the soft contribution to the Disc up to 3PM is clear, we proceed to check whether the t -pole is exactly canceled. Using the stationary phase method, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \oint_{C_{||}} \frac{ds}{s^2} M(s, b) &= 4 \text{Re} \left[\int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} \frac{ds}{s^2} i \left[1 - \exp\left(ia \frac{s}{\Lambda^2} + ia \frac{2G^2 s^2}{b^2 \Lambda^2} \frac{2i \log(s)}{\pi}\right) \right] \right] \\ &= 4i \text{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\Lambda^2} - \frac{1}{a \Lambda^2} \frac{i \left[\exp\left(ia - a \frac{4G^2 \Lambda^2}{\pi b^2} \log(\Lambda^2/m^2)\right) \right]}{1 + i \frac{4G^2 \Lambda^2}{\pi b^2} (2 \log(\Lambda^2/m^2) + 1)} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (98)$$

According to eq. (86), the t -pole is still exactly canceled, as all uncanceled terms are suppressed by $1/\log \Lambda_{\text{IR}}$.

Higher PM: soft dissipation causes the $\text{Disc} = 2i$ except in a small neighborhood of $s = 0$, where the higher-PM eikonal phase vanishes. Therefore,

holds at every PM order, meaning the t -pole is always canceled. In other words, the pure GR amplitude itself satisfies the high-energy limit

$$\oint_{|s| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{ds}{s^3} M(s, t) \sim \oint_{|s| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{ds}{s^2} M(s, b) \stackrel{\text{all PM}}{=} 0, \quad (100)$$

so we do not need to put any UV theory to help gravity satisfy the unitarity bound.

What can we learn?

We might have been overly cautious in the pure gravity calculation above. Both the 1PM phase shift and the

3PM dissipation are proportional to $\log \Lambda_{\text{IR}}$ —one real, one imaginary. They each cause the s -integral of the S -matrix in $M = i(1 - S)$ to vanish, leaving only the s -integral of the constant 1, which is $1/\Lambda^2$. This seems problematic: even when combining gravity and UV theories, the UV contributions appear as IR-finite corrections to the eikonal phase, which will be completely suppressed—just like the IR-finite terms at 2PM and 3PM. Thus, it appears that we cannot detect any UV information from the dispersion relation, which seems overly pessimistic.

However, if we look again at the distributions of Disc: the IR-divergent 1PM phase shift wipes out the IR-finite effects of Fig. 4 through rapid oscillations, while the IR-divergent 3PM dissipation in Fig. 6 is even more aggressive. Not only are UV effects invisible at the dispersion relation level (after s -integral), they disappear even at the amplitude level (before s -integral). Gravity acts like water in a pool: no matter what UV stones we throw in, we only see water. Perhaps draining the pool will reveal the UV. In other words, should we consider to bootstrap the undressed amplitude?

EQUIVALENCE OF SMEARED AND UNITARITY BOUNDS

The smeared bound proposed in [28]:

$$|\mathcal{M}_\Psi(s)| \leq s \times \text{constant} \quad (s \text{ is real}) \quad (101)$$

We think this is just the unitarity bound of amplitude, since smearing is essentially a numerical way of doing a Fourier transform—it just replaces plane waves with adjustable wave packets,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}(s, b) &= \int_{1/B}^{\infty} \frac{qdq}{2\pi} J_0(bq) \frac{\mathcal{M}(s, -q^2)}{2s}, \\ \mathcal{M}_\Psi(s) &= \int_{1/B}^M dq \Psi(q) \mathcal{M}(s, -q^2). \end{aligned} \quad (102)$$

The IR cutoff is introduced to avoid divergence. Since the Bessel- J_0 has the asymptotic form

$$\lim_{bq \gg 1} J_0(bq) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi bq}} \cos(bq - \pi/4). \quad (103)$$

The integral in eq. (102) effectively receives no contribution when $q \gg 1/b$ (due to rapid oscillations) or $q > M$. These two cutoffs are not fundamentally different. In comparison, the unitarity bound is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}(s, b) &= i(1 - \mathcal{S}(s, b)) \quad (s \text{ is real}), \\ 0 \leq \text{Im } \mathcal{M}(s, b) &\leq 2, \quad -1 \leq \text{Re } \mathcal{M}(s, b) \leq 1. \end{aligned} \quad (104)$$

Aside from a definitional difference from eq. (102), the smearing bound is just the unitarity upper bound[29].

The lower bound implies positivity, while the upper bound tells us that once $\mathcal{M}(s, b) \gtrsim 1$, the tree-level approximation breaks down and the scattering enters the black-disk regime.

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 - [8] In the conservative eikonal regime the long-range gravitational physics resides at finite b through the eikonal phase, while local EFT data are concentrated at $b \simeq 0$. This sharp separation is the basic reason why the bootstrap can be formulated directly in terms of undressed contact data.
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 - [15] $H(s, b)$ may contain higher-order singularities s^{-2} and s^{-3} at $s = 0$, but these do not affect any result. And the boundary integral of dressed H is always zero, i.e. $\oint_{C_\infty} ds e^{i\delta_0} H = 0$.
 - [16] In the eikonal regime the deflection angle is small, so $p_1 \parallel p_3$ and $p_2 \parallel p_4$, causing the little-group phases to cancel.
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 - [18] S. Caron-Huot, D. Mazac, L. Rastelli, and D. Simmons-Duffin, *JHEP* **07**, 110, [arXiv:2102.08951 \[hep-th\]](#).
 - [19] This isn't necessary, but it separates the contributions of the eikonal ladder and string resonances, so that they can be observed distinctly.
 - [20] Gribov *et al.* have shown in detail that spinning-particle scattering with 'nonsense' poles does not spoil the high-energy Regge behavior.
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 - [23] $-is$ actually originates from $-i\pi s + \mathcal{O}(t) = s \log(-s) + u \log(-u)$, which respects both crossing symmetry and analyticity.

- [24] This shows another advantage of $C_{|1|}$: since $|s|$ along the contour never become arbitrarily small, it ensures that aside from the oscillating factor governed by a , the remaining part varies slowly.
- [25] Could we say that if the dissipation Δ is induced by UV, then the inelastic cut gives the pure UV contribution? No—because gravity and UV are fully entangled through eikonal exponentiation. Dissipation just means the cut states include UV resonances, but they remain dressed by IR-divergent graviton loops.
- [26] Proof: Prepare a superposition state and compute the cross section $\langle A + z^* B | T^\dagger T | A + z B \rangle$. By varying the relative phase factor z , one can measure different cross sections and uniquely extract $\langle B | T^\dagger T | A \rangle$, i.e. the discontinuity. Hence, Disc is both observable and IR independent.
- [27] We can also verify that the Disc is indeed IR-independent by using IR Evolution Equations (IREE), similar to those employed by Recardo et al. at high energy lepton collider. Their inclusive cross-section calculations, like our Disc, require resummation over soft particles. By summing soft gravitons with energies in the strip

$$[\Lambda_{\text{IR}}, \Lambda_{\text{IR}} + \delta\Lambda_{\text{IR}}]$$

we obtain the IREE,

$$\delta \text{Disc}(s, b, \Lambda_{\text{IR}}) = \mathcal{K} \frac{\delta\Lambda_{\text{IR}}}{\Lambda_{\text{IR}}} \text{Disc}(s, b, \Lambda_{\text{IR}}) = 0.$$

(Unlike QED, Gravity has only soft and no collinear divergences, so the evolution is log rather than double-log.) Disc carries no gauge indices. In other words, the trivial gauge indices have already been summed over, which leads to a cancellation between the IR divergences arising from virtual graviton loops inside M/M^* and real graviton radiations between M and M^* in Fig. 6. Just like the KLN theorem for soft photons.

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- [29] Both are derived for real s ; extending them to complex s requires the polynomial boundedness of the amplitude.